

STUDY OF THE GRINDING PROCESS FRUITS FOR THE PRODUCTION OF JUICE WITH PULP

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Abstract. *The scientific research illustrates that from a physiological point of view, fruit and vegetable juices can be classified as nutritional drinks. They contain various food and biologically active substances and are a good source of water. Pulp juices contain most of the nutrients found in the original raw material. Juice consumption is constantly increasing all over the world. This is due to both the high nutritional value and the profitability of their production. The largest amount of juices is produced by the USA, the CIS countries, Italy, Germany, Bulgaria, France and Switzerland. The maximum level of fruit juice consumption per capita in the USA was 27 liters per year, in Switzerland - 24, in Sweden and in the Netherlands - 19 liters each. The consumption of juices is provided both by the own production of individual countries and by their import from other countries. Citrus juices are imported especially in large quantities, on the basis of which various blended juices and drinks.*

Key words: *grinding processes, external forces, processing fruits, grinding of materials, surface of solid materials.*

Introduction. Grinding is the process of increasing the surface of solid materials by crushing, splitting, abrasion and impact.

In the food industry, grinding is used to increase the surface of solid materials in order to increase the rate of biochemical and diffusion processes during the processing of fruits, vegetables, etc. as well as in the processing of food waste. Grinding is widely used in flour, meat, sugar beet, alcohol, brewing, canning and other industries.

Grinding processes are divided into crushing (coarse, medium and fine), grinding (fine and very fine) and cutting. Grinding machines can carry out a variety of grinding processes, ranging from crushing lumps to colloidal grinding, which makes it possible to obtain a product with particles with a size of 0.1 *microns*.

The grinding process is characterized by the degree of grinding, i.e. the ratio of the average size of a piece of material before grinding dH to the average size of a piece after grinding dK :

$$i = dH/dK \tag{1}$$

Typically, the pieces of material to be ground and the pieces or particles resulting from the grinding do not have the correct shape. In practice, the sizes of the pieces (dH And $d K$) is characterized by the size of the sieve openings through which bulk material is sieved before and after grinding.

Depending on the initial and final sizes of the largest pieces and particles of the grinding material, they are divided into the following types:

Type of grinding	dH ,(mm)	d K (mm)
large	1500...2000	250...25
Average	200...25	25...5
petty	25...5	5...1
1thin	5...1	1...0.075
colloidal	0.2...0.1	Up to 1* 10

Grinding of materials is carried out by crushing, splitting, impact and abrasion. During grinding, several accompanying types of grinding usually take place. For example, abrasion is accompanied by crushing, splitting, crushing upon impact. At abrasion of materials, a large amount of dust is formed and, in some cases, over-grinding takes place, which is sometimes unacceptable. The choice of grinding method depends on the size and strength of the pieces of crushed materials.

Strong and brittle materials are crushed by crushing and impact, strong and viscous materials - by crushing, viscous materials of medium strength - by abrasion, impact and splitting. Grinding is carried out in one or more examples, in open or closed cycles.

Closed circuit shredding, the pieces of material pass through the shredding machine once. If there is an admixture of fines in the source material, then it is preliminarily screened out. In an open cycle, as a rule, coarse and medium crushing is produced.

When grinding in a closed cycle after the grinding machine, a classifying device is installed, with the help of which pieces that exceed the established final size are again transported to the grinding machine for re-crushing.

Grinding processes are associated with the expenditure of a large amount of energy. Energy consumption can be determined from existing grinding theories.

The surface theory proceeds from the fact that, during grinding, work is spent on overcoming the forces of molecular attraction along the fracture surfaces of the material. It follows from this theory that the work required for grinding is proportional to the newly formed surface of the crushed material.

The volume theory proceeds from the fact that when grinding, the work is spent on the deformation of the material until the limiting destructive deformation is reached. It follows that the work required for grinding is proportional to the decrease in the volume of the pieces of material before their destruction.

The total work of external forces is expressed by the Rehbinder equation .

$$A = A_{\Delta} + A_{\Pi} = K_1 \Delta V + K_2 \Delta F \quad (2)$$

where A_{Δ} is the work expended on the deformation of the volume of the broken piece, J ; A_{Π} - work spent on the formation of a new surface, J; K_1 - coefficient of proportionality, equal work deformation of a unit volume of the body; ΔV - change in the volume of the destroyed body; K_2 - coefficient of proportionality, equal work spent on the formation of a unit of a new surface; ΔF is the increment of the newly formed surface.

Based on Hooke 's law, the work of deformation (in Nm) of a material under compression can be determined by the relation:

$$A_{\Delta} = \alpha^2 \Delta V / 2 E \quad (3)$$

where α is the destructive compressive stress, N/m; ΔV - reduction in the volume of pieces of material as a result of their deformation before destruction, m³; E is the modulus of elasticity of the material, N/m².

As can be seen from equation (3), the work expended on the destruction of the material depends on the breaking stress and the modulus of elasticity of the material.

Taking into account (3) we get:

$$A = (\alpha^2 \Delta V K / 2 E) + K_2 \Delta F \quad (4)$$

In the case of coarse crushing with a small degree of grinding, we can neglect the work expended on the formation of a new surface, and taking into account that $\Delta V \sim D^3$, we obtain

$$A = K_1 \Delta V = K_1 D^3 \quad (5)$$

where D is the characteristic piece size.

Equation (5) expresses the Kick-Kirpichev hypothesis: the work of crushing is proportional to the volume of the crushed piece.

For crushing with a high degree of grinding, one can neglect the work expended on deforming the volume of the piece. Then considering

$$A = K_2 \Delta F = K_2 D^2 \quad (6)$$

Rittinger's hypothesis, according to which the work of crushing is proportional to the size of the newly formed surface during crushing.

In the case when the terms in equation (2) cannot be neglected, the equation is obtained

$$A \approx K_3 \sqrt{D^2 D^3} \approx K_3 D^{2.5} \quad (7)$$

which is called the Bond equation: the work of crushing is proportional to the geometric mean of its volume and surface.

The work A_{pol} (in J) spent on cutting (cutting consists of two successive stages: first, the knife blade compresses the material, and then cuts through) can be expressed by the formula of Academician V.P. Goryachkin

$$A_{full} = A_{szh} + A_p \quad (8)$$

where A_{szh} - work expended on compressing the product, J; A_p - useful work of cutting, J.

The work of compression $A_{ck} = E \cdot h_{ck} / h$ where E is the conditional modulus of compression of the material by the knife blade, J, A_{com} is the height of the compressed layer, m; h_{szh} - the initial height of the material layer, m.

Usually they use the concept of "specific cutting force", which is the force related to 1 meter of the length of the knife blade. Thus, the specific cutting force for carrots is 1400...1600 N/m, and for potatoes - 600...700 N/m.

The conditional modulus of material compression by a knife blade is determined experimentally. Its value depends on the properties of the material, the type of knife, force and other factors [9].

Rittinger’s law (1867) according to this law, the work spent on grinding the material is proportional to the newly formed surface. Rittinger proceeds mainly from the concept that the useful work of grinding is completely converted into surface energy.

In general form, Rittinger’s law can be written like this

$$W = K_1 \left(\frac{1}{d} - \frac{1}{D} \right) \tag{9}$$

where W is the work of grinding: D and d are the particle sizes before and after grinding, respectively, and K_1 is a constant value.

If the ratio $n = D/d$ is denoted as the degree of grinding, then this formula takes the form

$$W = K_1 \left(\frac{n-1}{D} \right) \tag{10}$$

Kick’s Law (1885). The work required by Kick’s law for similar changes in the configurations of geometrically similar bodies from the same material varies in proportion to the volumes or weights of these bodies. Kik suggests that the destruction of two identical pieces occurs in the same way and leads to the formation of pieces of the same size. In general form, Kick’s law can be expressed

$$W = K_2 \log D / d \tag{11}$$

If we introduce the degree of grinding n into this formula, then the formula can be written as follows.

$$W = K_2 \log n \tag{12}$$

Mechanical grinding of raw materials is based on the application of external forces exceeding the molecular cohesive forces.

Crushing causes deformation of the product. According to the theory of elasticity, the absolute work of deformation is in (J).

$$A = \sigma V / 2E \tag{13}$$

where σ is the voltage, Pa; E is the modulus of elasticity of the first kind, Pa; V is the volume of the deformable material, m^3 .

The work of deformation of a body before failure, referred to a unit volume ($H=A/V$), for a given material is a constant value characterizing its structural and mechanical properties. It has been experimentally established that 0.8-1.0 kJ of energy should be spent on crushing 1 kg of mass, 1.25-1.5 kJ of 1 kg of apples.

Crushing can be considered as a process of increasing the specific surface, and it is advisable to characterize the state of material crushing by the size of the specific surface S . For a ball with a diameter D , the specific surface area (in cm^{-1})

$$S_{yo} = \frac{S}{V} = \pi D^2 / \frac{1}{6} \pi D^3 = 6/D \quad (14)$$

It follows that the specific surface area is inversely proportional to the linear dimensions of the body. Determination of the specific surface of finely divided materials by analytical or experimental means under production conditions is difficult, since the methods for calculating the total surface of finely divided systems are complex. Therefore, the state of grinding is determined by the size of an individual particle of crushed material or by the reciprocal of this size - the degree of dispersion.

Real systems are made up of particles of different sizes. To determine the average degree of dispersion of a polydisperse system, the total volume of all particles is found, and knowing that the number n determines the degree of dispersion as a value reciprocal to the radius of the particle averaged over the volume.

$$\frac{1}{r_{\text{срд}}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{4/3\pi n}{\int_0^x \varphi(x) dx}} \quad (15)$$

Where $\int_0^x \varphi(x) dx$ is the total volume of all particles from 0 to x .

By integration, this total volume can be calculated if a suitable analytical expression for the frequency curve is known

$y = \varphi(x)$, where y is the content of particles of size x as a percentage of the total number.

For practical purposes, simple and convenient for industrial use methods for determining the average dispersion of mixtures have been developed. For some products, sieve analysis is used during canning. In this case, with the help of lattice classifiers, a material sample is divided into size fractions.

A sieve classifier is a device with a set of sieves located one above the other with different holes in each sieve, but the same holes in each of them. After sieving the sample of the crushed product, the amount of residue at the bottom of the classifier and on each of the sieves is determined. From these data, the weighted average diameter (in mm) is easily determined.

$$M = \frac{\frac{d_0+d_1}{2}p_0 + \frac{d_1+d_2}{2}p_1 + \frac{d_2+d_3}{2}p_2 + \dots + \frac{d_{n-1}+d_n}{2}p_n}{100} \tag{16}$$

where $p_0, p_1, p_2 \dots \dots p_n$ - mass amounts of the residue, respectively, at the bottom of the classifier and on individual sieves of the total amount of the test sample; $p_0, p_1, p_2 \dots \dots p_n$ - the diameters of the holes of the respective sieves, mm (d_0 - the maximum diameter of the holes).

The degree of crushing of fruits significantly affects the processes of obtaining juice (the duration of the juice output, the content of suspended particles, etc.). The presence of a large number of small particles makes it difficult to clean the juice from the pulp. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out crushing in such a way that the resulting crushed mixture (pulp) has an optimal granulometric composition, depending on the method of obtaining juice. Mechanical grinding can be done by crushing or cutting.

To calculate the work expended on cutting the product, experimental data are used on the magnitude of the force P , which must be applied to the edge of a knife 1 cm long (Table 1). The specific work of cutting W is defined as the product of the effort P on the path / (in kJ/sm^2)

$$W = P \cdot l \tag{17}$$

Tab. 1

No.	Product	P, kJ/cm	W, kJ / cm 2
1.	Carrot	14-16	0.014-0.016
2.	Onion	17-18	0.017-0.018
3.	Cabbage	10-12	0.010-0.012
4.	Beets (boiled)	9-11	0.009-0.011
5.	Potato	6-7	0.006-0.007

As a result of studying the process of grinding fruits and vegetables, analyzing the current state of the production of juices with pulp, as well as analyzing existing machines and mechanisms for grinding fruits and vegetables, we came to the conclusion that in the modern time of a market economy, it is necessary to create new technological lines, machines and mechanisms to reduce waste output. and increase the yield of juices when grinding fruits and vegetables.

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